

FDO Forum Document Standards

Version 1.1

FDO Forum Working Draft 29 January 2022

Current and previous versions:

V1.0: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XrHRDk-l9wbqcwKAm2b_TBKCRg_gaVcONiBfRTGfDD0/edit

internal: <https://datashare.rzg.mpg.de/apps/files/?dir=/FDO-Forum/FDO-Document-Store&fileid=206078478>

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Abstract

The FDO Forum differentiates between different types of documents such as

1. Documents that will include specifications for FDOs which are of relevance for all persons engaged in FDO usage and which therefore will have binding functions. These documents which we call “FDO Recommendations” will need to undergo a phased process of review and endorsement.
2. Documents from external bodies which will play an important role in specifying and using FDOs. These need to be compliant with the FDO Recommendations and thus

need to be endorsed by the FDO Forum. Obviously, a shorter process will be required.

3. Documents that will have a role in defining FDO Forum activities, but will not influence the FDO specifications directly (scoping documents, event announcements, liaison documents, etc.).

In this paper we will primarily describe the process for FDO Recommendations of type 1 and the special process for documents from external bodies.

Status of this document

This document is a Working Draft of a recommendation track document that has been discussed in the FDO TSIG Working Group and therefore needs to be discussed and endorsed by the FDO Forum as version WD 1.0, i.e., it will be the FDO Steering Committee which will have to finally endorse this document after having followed the process described in this document.

It will be the first document following these principles and other documents will follow. We will use [Google Drive](#) to host the documents in the different phases of internal Forum and external Community commenting and support dynamic entry of comments.

The URL of the shared drive will be mentioned in the corresponding documents and requests for comments.

Acknowledgments

This document is based on the IVOA Document Standards v2.0 (<https://www.ivoa.net/documents/DocStd/>) which were adapted from the W3C documentation standards. It has been adapted to meet the FDO Forum requirements.

Contributions from various FDO Forum Groups were used to create this WD.

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1. Document types

The FDO Forum publishes three types of documents:

Recommendation track documents. These are specifications, guidelines, etc. produced by Working Groups to specify FDOs and guide FDO implementations. Documents on the Recommendation track may progress from Working Drafts (WD) in two phases to Proposed Recommendations (PR) and finally to Recommendations (REC).

Endorsed Document track documents. An FDO Forum Endorsed Document is a document produced outside of the FDO Forum which is subject to a review process, but not as heavyweight as the recommendation track process. Documents on the Endorsed Document track will be suggested (SUG) to the FDO Forum for endorsement. It will be studied (STD) by an FDO Forum group and suggested as a Proposed Endorsed Document (PED), to then become an FDO Endorsed Document (ED).

FDO Forum Notes. An FDO Forum Note is a dated, public record of an idea, comment, or document that will not directly influence FDO specifications (scoping documents, event announcements, liaison documents, etc.). Authorship of a Note may vary greatly (e.g., by an FDO Forum Working Group, by an FDO Forum member, etc.). FDO Forum Notes can be turned into an Proposed Endorsed Note (PEN), to then become an FDO Endorsed Note (EN).

Finalized documents approved by the FDO Executive Board to become public will be made available on the FDO Forum's open repository [Zenodo](#). The FDO Forum Executive Board appoints a Documentation Coordinator (DC) who oversees the document collection and assures that documents conform to these guidelines.

The DC may reformat, rename, or renumber documents so as to conform to changes in FDO Forum practice (e.g., changes to document styles or the "Status of this Document" section).

Each public document must clearly indicate whether it is a Note, Working Draft (WD), Proposed Recommendation (PR), Recommendation (REC), Proposed Endorsed Document (PED), Endorsed Document (ED), Proposed Endorsed Note (PEN), or Endorsed Note (EN).

The primary language for FDO Forum documents is English.

1.1 Status

Each document must include a section about the status of the document. The status section should explain why FDO Forum has published the document, whether or not it is part of the Recommendation track, who developed it, where to send comments about it, whether implementation experience is being sought, any significant changes from the previous version, and any other relevant meta-information.

The status section of a Working Draft must set expectations about the stability of the work (e.g., that it may be superseded, obsoleted, or dropped at any time, that it should not be cited as other than a work in progress, etc.) and must indicate how much consensus within FDO Forum there is about the Working Draft (e.g., no consensus, consensus among the Working Group participants, etc.).

The status section of a Note must indicate the level of endorsement within or by FDO Forum for the material in the Note, and set expectations about future commitments from FDO Forum to pursue the topics covered by the Note or to respond to comments about the Note.

1.2 Document Registration

All documents and subsequent versions must be registered in the FDO Forum [Document Management Register](#) (Google spreadsheet) located in the [Standards Documents](#) folder on the shared [FDO Forum Google Drive](#). The Register is only accessible to Working Group chairs and the Executive Board, although a [viewable public version](#) is located in the [Forum's Public Folder](#).

In the Document Management Register 'ALL DOCS' worksheet, data should only be input in the shaded columns as all other columns are auto-generated or linked to office automation software. The ALL DOCS worksheet auto-generates the document filename (in the format specified in *1.3 Naming and version numbering conventions* below) based on input values. In addition to generating the filename, the worksheet also captures the document review date, its Google Drive URL location, and contact and contact email. The specific cell containing the document review date will be green if the date is greater than a week away; yellow if the review date falls within the coming week, and red if the review date has passed.

The Document Management Register also contains supplementary worksheets listing documents by Working Group and a worksheet containing the FDO Forum Master Mailing List. These are live auto-generated informational worksheets and thus are locked and cannot be modified.

For accessibility or spreadsheet errors, please contact the Document Coordinator at secretariat@fairdo.org.

1.3 Naming and version numbering conventions

FDO Forum document name has four components:

1. A document type code:

	Internal/ External	Code
Recommendation		
Working Draft	I	WD
Proposed	I	PR
Recommendation	I	REC
Endorsed Document		
Suggestion	E	SUG
Study	E	STD
Proposed	E	PED
Endorsed Document	E	ED

Note

Proposed	I	PEN
Endorsed Note	I	EN

2. A concise name, which should be a reasonable condensation of the document title.
3. A version number of the form I.J, where I and J are integers 0, 1, 2, ... 9, 10, 11,
4. A date. The date is the GMT date on which the current version of the document was produced, in the format YYYYMMDD. (This does not allow for multiple revisions of a document to be released within one 24-hour period.)

The four components are concatenated, separated by hyphens.

Version numbers follow these guidelines:

The number to the left of the (first) decimal point starts with 0 for documents that are being discussed within a Working Group prior to publication for FDO Forum-wide review. The number increments to 1 for the first public version, and to 2, 3, ..., for subsequent versions that are not backward compatible and/or require substantial revisions to implementations.

The number to the right of the decimal point is an integer counter, beginning with 0 and increasing in simple cardinal order (0, 1, 2, ... 9, 10, 11, ...). This number does not track every revision to a document, but rather, denotes a logical version or conceptually consistent view. This number should only be incremented when there are significant and substantial changes to text but few (minor) or no changes required of implementations. The version number normally remains fixed as a document is promoted from Working Draft to Proposed Recommendation to Recommendation, with editorial revisions indicated by the change of date.

After a document reaches Recommendation or Endorsed Note status, subsequent revisions retrace the promotion process. Changes that are backward compatible result in increments in the number to the right of the decimal place (1.1, 1.2, ...). Changes that are not backward compatible require an increment of the number of the left of the decimal place (2.0), with subsequent backward compatible revisions following the same pattern (2.1, 2.2, ...).

The final published and approved Recommendation retains the date on the title page of the document, but the date is removed from the document filename in order to simplify reference to the document.

The following examples show a typical name and numbering progression for a sample document.

NOTE-MyNewIdea-1.0-20081001.pdf	(initial idea)
WD-ConciseName-0.1-20081225.pdf	(first Working Draft, in WG)
WD-ConciseName-0.1-20081231.pdf	(revised 6 days later)
WD-ConciseName-0.2-20090115.pdf	(text revised substantially)
WD-ConciseName-0.2-20090201.pdf	(final version in WG before PR)
WD-ConciseName-1.0-20090301.pdf	(published first version to FDO Forum)
PR-ConciseName-1.0-20090501.pdf	(promoted to PR)
PR-ConciseName-1.0-20090615.pdf	(updated after RFC)
PR-ConciseName-1.0-20090801.pdf	(updated after EB review)
REC-ConciseName-1.0.pdf	(accepted as REC; date, e.g., 20090901 appears on title page)
WD-ConciseName-1.1-20100628.pdf	(first update to WD in WG; does not affect implementation)
WD-ConciseName-1.1-20100715.pdf	(revised text)
WD-ConciseName-1.1-20100801.pdf	(revised text)
PR-ConciseName-1.1-20100815.pdf	(promoted to PR)
PR-ConciseName-1.1-20100915.pdf	(updated after RFC/EB review)
PR-ConciseName-1.1-20101001.pdf	(updated after RFC/EB review)
REC-ConciseName-1.1.pdf	(accepted as REC)
WD-ConciseName-2.0-20110628.pdf	(major update to WD in WG; does affect implementation)
WD-ConciseName-2.0-20110715.pdf	(revised text)
WD-ConciseName-2.0-20110801.pdf	(revised text)

PR-ConciseName-2.0-20110815.pdf	(promoted to PR)
PR-ConciseName-2.0-20110915.pdf	(updated after RFC/EB review)
PR-ConciseName-2.0-20111001.pdf	(updated after RFC/EB review)
REC-ConciseName-2.0.pdf	(accepted as REC)

In the case of an Endorsed Note making reference to an existing recommendation, it is recommended that the Concise Name of Endorsed Notes includes a reference to the Concise Name used in the relevant REC, and an indication of its relationship to the REC (e.g. ConciseName-Implementation).

Names will be reviewed and may be modified by the Document Coordinator to be consistent with these conventions. All documents in phases WD1.x and higher are stored in the FDO Forum document repository:

<https://datashare.rzg.mpg.de/apps/files/?dir=/FDO-Forum/FDO-Document-Store&fileid=206078478>

1.4 Format

Documents made available for comment must be MSWord (.docx) or GoogleDoc documents and placed in the appropriate document root folder.

The standard format for FDO Forum documents is PDF, though any document preparation tools may be used that allow for the publication of PDF and that retain the standard formatting elements and style. In December 2021, document templates were provided for MSWord and as Open Document Text Format. Information about the current document templates can be found at

<https://datashare.rzg.mpg.de/apps/files/?dir=/FDO-Forum/FDO-Document-Store/FDO%20Document%20Templates&fileid=206080726>. The document source in its original format should also be submitted and retained in the FDO Forum document collection.

1.4 How to publish a document

Documents are entered into the FDO Forum Document Collection by the Document Coordinator in response to a request from a Steering Committee Chair, Working Group chair or the person primarily responsible for editing a particular document. The technical details of the submission process are determined by the document coordinator together with the SC. Current information is available on a web page linked from the FDO Forum document repository. Absolute path names must be avoided when packaging the document(s) as well as when creating internal links within the document.

When problems are encountered during the submission process (e.g., unavailability of the site or too large files), it is necessary to agree with the DC on different means of electronic transfer.

1.5 Supplementary resources

The Document Coordinator maintains a repository of supplementary resources, such as XML schema, RDF vocabulary definitions, etc. Developers and any type of validation system/service should use these in preference to copies stored elsewhere. There is, however, no requirement to use them if a different implementation yields compliance with a given recommendation. Such additional items are considered part of the implementation but not part of the recommendation itself. Recommendation document authors should, however, reference them as informative appendices if applicable and seek consistency. A FAIR Digital Object repository to encompass or link to all these accompanying information artifacts will be provided so that reliable and complete information can be provided at all times. At the same time, authors of auxiliary files should include comments stating which standards and versions thereof they support.

More details will need to be worked out depending on actual cases.

2. Recommendation process

2.1 Process Actors

Formal actors in the process for FDO Forum Recommendations are the

- editors in general members of an FDO Forum WG,
- authors in general members of an FDO Forum WG,
- members of an FDO Forum WG,
- FDO Forum WG chairs,
- FDO Forum Steering Committee (SC),
- FDO Forum Executive Board (EB),
- RDA DFIG Chairs,
- FDO Community (COM) which are those experts registered at the FDO email list fdo@mpcdf.mpg.de

2.2 Process Description

Formal

The FDO Forum recommendation process is used to build consensus to foster the specifications and implementations around FAIR Digital Objects. FDO Forum Working Drafts

become Recommendations by following a process defined in this document. The shown diagram summarizes this process of increasing levels of maturity and consensus.

Note. An FDO Forum Note is a dated, public record of an idea, comment, practice, experience, insight, advice, guideline, or policy. Authorship of a Note may vary greatly (e.g., by one or several FDO Forum Working Group, by an FDO Forum member, etc.). In some circumstances a Note may be the basis for a Working Draft. In cases where Notes have public relevance, SC can decide to make them public, adhering to specific formats to be defined.

Working Draft version 0.x. A document begins on the recommendation track as a Working Draft with versions 0.x. Such a Working Draft is a chartered work item of one or several Working Groups and generally represents work in progress. The version “0.x” indicates that this WG is still being discussed in the WG(s) to reach a state of consensus which is indicated by the WG chairs.

Working Draft version I.J. (I > 0) A document has found consensus within the authoring WG and is now ready to be discussed within the FDO Forum, i.e., it is being submitted to SC and other WGs for commenting. The document continues on the recommendation track as a Working Draft with versions I.J with I greater than 0. It still represents work in progress within the FDO F including a commitment by FDO Forum to pursue work in this particular area.

Proposed Recommendation. A document has found consensus within the FDO F and is now issued as a Proposed Recommendation to the community of FDO experts which can be found in RDA and the FDO Community of registered experts. FDO EB will need to assess the state of consensus and also assess compliance with the relevant requirements of the Working Group's charter and any accompanying requirements documents, existence of sufficient implementation experience and sufficient reflection on reviewers' comments before taking this step.

FDO Forum Recommendation. An FDO Forum Recommendation is a document that is the end result of extensive consensus-building within the FDO community of interested and registered experts about FDO specifications. FDO Forum SC considers that the details specified by a Recommendation are appropriate for widespread deployment and promote the implementation of FDOs globally.

Endorsement by External Bodies. FDO Forum not only will endorse specifications made by other organisations (see chapter 3), but FDO Forum Recommendations can also become subject of endorsement or standardization processes of external organizations such as RDA, ISO etc. FDO Forum cannot exclude that refinements and adaptations of the recommendations will result from these endorsements processes. In this case the Recommendations will be subject to changes requiring starting a new phase as Proposed Recommendation.

Generally, Working Groups create Working Drafts with the intent of advancing them through the standards process. However, publication of a document at one maturity level does not guarantee that it will advance to the next. Some documents may be dropped as active work or may be subsumed by other documents. If, at any maturity level of the standards process, work on a document ceases (e.g., because a Working Group or activity closes, or because the work is subsumed by another document), a final version of the document should be issued and stored in the “Historical” category, with the status section noting that work on this document has concluded, and for what rationale, and with links provided to relevant follow-on documents. Any time a document advances to a higher maturity level, the announcement of the transition must indicate any formal objections. If, at any maturity level prior to Recommendation, review comments or implementation experience result in substantive changes to a document, the document should be returned to Working Draft for further work.

Some documents which are not FDO Forum Recommendations may require discussion, evaluation and endorsement. They are subject to a lighter-weight endorsement process, the Endorsed Note one, which is described in Section 3.

2.3 Working Draft (WD)

FDO Forum official documents begin as Working Drafts. Working Drafts are first the purview of a Working Group[1]. Working Drafts may undergo numerous revisions during their development first within the proposing WG and subsequently within the FDO Forum. During this volatile phase Working Drafts are not included in the formal FDO Forum collection of recommendations, but rather are maintained dependent on its status by the responsible working group in FDO Forum’s document repository.

Entrance criteria. A Working Draft is published at the discretion of a Working Group once the WG is satisfied that the document is sufficiently developed to merit broader exposure and feedback. Publication of a Working Draft is not an assertion of consensus, of endorsement, or of technical and editorial quality. Consensus is not a prerequisite for approval to publish; the

Working Group may request publication of a Working Draft even if it is unstable and does not meet all Working Group requirements. Working Drafts are subject to review by the EB and the document coordinator for compliance to these guidelines.

Ongoing work. Once a Working Draft has been published, the Working Group should continue to develop it by encouraging review and feedback first within (phase 1) and then outside (phase 2) of the FDO Forum. Visibility of comments to all FDO Forum members is achieved by using a shared document and making the URL available to all FDO Forum members. The EB may decide to classify a Working Drafts which is no longer under development in the “Historical” category.

Next maturity level. After a suitable review and trial period, the chair of the Working Group may suggest to EB to promote the Working Draft to a Proposed Recommendation. Such advancement should occur only when the chair of the Working Group and SC are satisfied that consensus has been reached, and more formal and extensive review is now warranted. Advancement to Proposed Recommendation implies:

1. The Working Group has fulfilled the relevant requirements of the Working Group charter(s) and those of any accompanying requirements documents.
2. The Working Group has formally addressed issues raised during the development and review process (possibly modifying the document).
3. The Working Group has reported all formal objections.
4. When applicable, the Working Group should be able to demonstrate an interoperable implementation of each feature, and validation tools should be made available. The rules for implementation references can be specific to a working group. If the chair of the Working Group believes that broader review is critical, the chair may advance the document to Proposed Recommendation even without adequate implementation experience or validation tool availability. In this case, the document status section should indicate why the chair promoted the document directly to Proposed Recommendation. A report describing the implementations or any associated validation tools should be published as a Note, or should be documented as part of the Request for Comments (see below).

2.4 Proposed Recommendation (PR)

Entrance criteria. Proposed Recommendations are published by the chair of a Working Group following the criteria described above. Proposed Recommendations are considered to be technically mature and ready for FDO COM wide review.

Ongoing work. The Working Group should continue to encourage review and feedback within and outside of the FDO Forum. The EB may decide to classify the Proposed Recommendations which are no longer under development in the “Historical” category.

Next maturity level. The chair of the Working Group that developed the Proposed Recommendation may call for a formal Request for Comments (RFC). The RFC is sent to the widest possible FDO Forum distribution list (fdo@mpcdf.mpg.de), the RDA using RDA FDO DF IG as mediator and published by adding a link to the RFC on the FDO Forum document repository web page. Distribution of the RFC initiates a 1-month public review period. All comments submitted during this review period must be posted publicly and responded to publicly. This will be achieved by using a shared document accessible to the FDO Community.

Following the RFC period, the editor(s) may issue additional document versions that take into account the comments received in order to reach consensus, or the WG Chair may decide to return the document to Working Draft status if the maturity level appears not to be sufficient. Such a decision needs to be documented and made available to the FDO Forum. The WG Chairs indicate the availability of the new version on the RFC page and publishes the information to the same wide distribution list, with a link to the RFC and the information that comments on this new version should be posted within two weeks. In particular, parties who made comments during the RFC are invited to indicate whether they see their comments suitably addressed; the WG chairs may issue additional document versions in order to reach a consensus. The SC then has two weeks to make a final review of the document and to issue a final binary approval (yes/no) noted on the RFC public comment website (“SC vote”).

PRs being brought forward for promotion to REC should, when applicable, have at least an interoperable implementation and validation tools should be made available. In its final review the SC may agree to waive these requirements if there are extenuating circumstances. If the SC does not agree to waive the requirement regarding interoperable implementations and/or availability of validation tools, but there are otherwise no outstanding issues or unresolved problems, the final decision on promotion of the PR to REC rests with the EB.

The EB, working in consultation with the chairs of the Working Group responsible for the PR, then makes a final summary recommendation, including information about the availability of reference implementations and validation tools, and the EB forwards this recommendation to the SC for review and approval. If the EB is satisfied that the procedure has been properly followed, they promote the document to a Recommendation.

2.5 Recommendation (REC)

Entrance criteria. Recommendations are published by the FDO Forum EB following the criteria described above. Recommendations are the final form of FDO Forum documents and constitute an FDO Guideline.

Ongoing work. The WG chairs in cooperation with the document editors should prepare a “full standards package” for the new REC and submit it as an FDO to an FDO compliant repository.

Recommendations may need to be revised and extended as time goes on. Significant revisions of Recommendations must proceed through the Working Draft and Proposed Recommendation phases. A significant revision is any revision that requires changes in software based on the document. Errata can be attached to a Recommendation following the procedure described in section 4. Further work on the evolution of the recommendation is documented in the relevant Working Group pages.

Next maturity level. A Recommendation is the highest level of maturity for an FDO Forum document. The FDO Forum EB may propose that Recommendations be endorsed as standards by external organizations such as RDA and DIN/ISO.

2.6 Document promotion process summary

The FDO Forum document promotion process is summarized in graphical form in the figure above.

1. Editors and authors of a Working Group prepare a Working Draft (version 0.1) and signal its existence to the Document Coordinator to include it in the Document Process Table.
2. Working Group members review the Working draft and if applicable look at reference implementations and validation tools. The Chairs of the Working Group, with consent of the WG, promote the document to WD with version ≥ 1.0 when consensus is achieved.
3. Working Group chairs submit Working Draft (version ≥ 1.0) to Document Coordinator for posting in the FDO Forum document collection.
4. FDO Forum groups (SC and WGs) review the Working Draft (WD) and if applicable look at reference implementations and validation tools. An FDO Forum internal RFC is issued to all groups in the FDO Forum. A minimum comment period of 1 month must be allowed.
5. The Chairs of the Working Group and the EB, promote the document to a Proposed Recommendation (PR) when consensus has been achieved and submits it to the Document Coordinator for posting in the FDO Forum document collection as PR.
6. The EB issues a formal Request for Comments (RFC) to the e-mail distribution list fdo@mpcdf.mpg.de and to the chairs of RDA DFIG. The RFC and all comments must be logged on a globally editable shared document whose URL is given in the RFC to the FDO COM. A minimum comment period of 1 month must be allowed. All registered members of the FDO Community are required to examine Proposed Recommendations

during the RFC period and to post comments in the public shared document. It is up to RDA DFIG how they want to mediate the reviews within their community.

7. The editor(s) in interaction with the authors and the WG chairs respond to comments on the shared document. If comments lead to significant changes to the document, the WG Chairs may decide in interaction with the EB to revert the document status to Working Draft (back to Step 1).
8. If comments are addressed to the satisfaction of the WG Chairs and EB, the WG Chairs request a final vote, to be completed within 4 weeks by the SC. For this purpose the EB, working in consultation with the chairs of the Working Group responsible for the PR, makes a final summary recommendation and submits the PR to the SC for approval.
9. The EB formally needs to state that there is consensus within the FDO Forum for promotion to Recommendation.
10. If yes, the EB reports on approval to the Document Coordinator and WG Chairs and asks the Document Coordinator to update the document status to Recommendation. If no, the concerns need to be resolved by the Editors in interaction with the WG chairs and a new poll will be taken, or if serious revisions are required, the document would revert to Step 1.
11. The EB may take further steps to outside organizations to endorse the recommendation.

3. Endorsed Notes and Documents process

Some internal notes and external documents require an endorsement by FDO Forum but a lighter weight review process than the one undergone by the FDO Forum Recommendations is required. They follow the Endorsed Notes and Documents process, managed by the chairs of an assigned WG in interaction with the EB. This is the case for instance for documents provided by external organizations which are influencing the FDO specifications.

Entrance criteria. Endorsed Notes and Documents can be proposed by a Working Group, the EB and SC. They will be discussed in the FDO Forum by all groups until consensus about approval has been achieved. The endorsement process is managed by the WG chairs in interaction with the EB.

In the case of serious deviating opinions, the comments from FDO Forum need to be summarized by the WG chairs in interaction with the EB and submitted to the originating bodies to resolve the aspects indicated. Otherwise, the EB will suggest approval by the Steering Committee which will take a final decision.

Endorsed Documents. Endorsed Notes and Documents have been endorsed by the Steering Committee and the Document Coordinator will be informed to integrate it in the list of endorsed notes and documents in the FDO Forum document collection as EN resp. ED.

4. The document collection

The FDO Forum document collection is the primary source for FDO Forum documents. FDO Forum users, especially from outside the forum, should always be directed to the document collection rather than be sent private copies of documents.

The FDO Forum document collection is organized so as to lead readers most naturally to the current versions of all documents in all document classes. A document archive is also maintained so that previous published versions of documents remain available. The archive also contains the “Historical” documents.

5. Changes from previous versions

This version 1.1 has the status of a WD to be discussed in the FDO Forum. The comments made to the version 1.0 were light (typos etc.) and have all been dealt with in agreement. The reactions to the comments can be found in the archived 1.0 version.

[1] In the case that a WD is being proposed by several WGs all chairs are involved in the process.